

Seeing the dust for the trees: integrative modelling of timber co-products for design-to- fabrication workflows

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Abstract. By mapping material properties that influence mechanical performance across the timber resource at a high spatial resolution and matching them to digitally simulated performance demands in designed glulam elements (Fig. 1), workflows such as the RawLam Experiments hint towards the ability to use material stocks usually unemployed in glulam manufacturing. However, the broader implications of this highly tailored and selective process remain to be quantitatively evaluated, examining the increase in timber resource used for construction and addressing how waste generation in the RawLam process is measured against established glulam fabrication methods. The paper presents possible scenarios for an industrial scale-up of the process and an evaluation of the co-product cascade associated to each scenario. Findings on the cascade variations are then leveraged to put in place a new version of the RawLam allocation procedure. This paper reveals the key differences between the standard sawmilling and glulam production process and the RawLam method in terms of the specific production steps involved and the resultant impacts on co-product ratios. This enables an evaluation of the perceived benefits of the RawLam approach to design modelling glulam blanks against broader metrics of economic value and carbon sequestration. As part of a larger effort to integrate a wider segment of the timber value chain into architectural design processes, this work demonstrates how industry-relevant indicators such as the value impacts of the co-product cascade can help steer the design modelling of engineered timber elements.

Keywords: RawLam, glulam manufacturing, timber industry, co-products cascade

Fig. 1. The allocation of lamellae onto sawn boards. Colors indicate where material properties either exceed (blue) or fall short of (red) simulated performance demands.

1. Introduction

As the construction industry struggles to find ways to reduce its impact on the natural environment, timber is considered one of the most promising avenues for reducing GHG emissions in the field. However, the shift towards it entails an increased pressure on forestry, and therefore necessitates a better understanding of wood resources, enabling their more sustainable exploitation. To permit such understanding, ongoing research develops means of tackling the inherent heterogeneity of wood in design computation workflows [1][2][3][4]. As part of this line of enquiry, the RawLam Experiments (Fig. 2) developed by CITA have demonstrated the potential of these workflows for a bespoke and materially sensitive approach to fabricating tailored glue-laminated

timber beams [5][6]. By mapping material properties that influence mechanical performance across the timber resource at a high spatial resolution and matching them to digitally simulated performance demands in designed glulam elements, the RawLam Experiments' workflow hints at the ability to use material stocks usually unemployed in glulam manufacturing. It allows a more strategic usage of materials, deploying more of the available timber resource for construction.

Fig. 2. The second phase of RawLam 3, part of the RawLam experiments.

However, the broader implications of this highly tailored and selective process remain to be quantitatively evaluated, understanding the sustainability of such practices and aligning with growing concern in the forestry industry on this matter [7]. This paper examines the increase in timber resources used for construction and addresses how waste generation in the RawLam process is measured against established glulam fabrication methods. A similar assessment was previously conducted on RawLam, considering Non-Hazardous Waste Disposed (HWD), Components for Reuse (CRU) and Materials for Recycling (MFR) indicators [8]. This research focuses on co-product generation rather than waste, taking the perspective of the sawmill industry on valorization of waste products in the fabrication of glulam and other high-value sawn wood products.

Generally, the timber industry has growingly relied on digital methods for the fabrication of such products [9]. The current approach in sawmilling can be broadly described as “pushing” material: the final products and their value are only known after the sawmilling process, meaning that products are generated and then matched to the market. The objective, however, is to change this approach to one of “pulling” material

through the sawmill: high value products are identified within logs before sawing using technologies such as X-ray computed tomography (CT) scanning and only those products are extracted. This would ensure that the products more precisely match market demand and open possibilities of highly tailored building elements. These developments are being aided by the increasing fidelity and information generation capacity of in-line digital sensors in sawmilling, such as CT scanning [10]. The ability of RawLam to make a precise use of the resource based on its estimated performance, and therefore the ability to leverage timber resources usually neglected in construction products, make this process a highly relevant candidate for initiating such a shift.

RawLam allocation process

At the core of the RawLam Experiments is an allocation process – the allocator – which, within a high-resolution volumetric map of material properties of the harvested log, attempts to place a collection of lamellae that belong to specific glulam beams (Fig. 1). The material properties are used to create a nominal “quality” map across the logs. Mechanical simulations of the glulam beams under specific loading conditions provide a map of performance demands. The central task of the allocator is therefore to create a good match between available material quality and the highly localized performance demands of each glulam lamella. In this sense, it is a good example of the “pull” approach to product extraction from the forest resource. The allocator is integrated into a digital design workflow where a glulam assembly can be mechanically simulated and then allocated to specific log datasets.

So far, two approaches have guided the allocation logic: the best match between the simulated mechanical performance demands across each lamella and the material property distribution of the resource; and the tight packing of lamellae onto sawn boards to be able to maximize the exploitation of the sawn boards. While these approaches aim for a more efficient material usage for a glulam beam of comparable stiffness than with traditional methods, they do not consider the finer nuances of industrial sawmilling, namely the ratios between sawmilling co-products – lumber, chips, shavings, and sawdust.

Fig. 3. Aligning features from the CT scan with the sawn board in RawLam.

Fig. 4. Typical log sawing pattern (left) versus the plain-sawing used for RawLam (right). Green indicates parts of the log that are turned into chip co-products. Chips are typically valued at 20% of the value of sawn lumber. Sawdust is valued between 50-90% of chips.

Prospective scenario modelling for waste assessment

The calculation of the RawLam cascade was performed across three different prospective scenarios [11] and compared with a glulam scenario (Fig. 5). This scenario modeling has been performed in collaboration with Swedish timber producer Norra Timber to frame potential industrial scale-ups for RawLam. Part of the scenarios' objective is to understand the ability to produce RawLam in current sawmills and under what conditions the industrialization of the process would be enabled. As sawmills differ vastly in the equipment that they host [12][13], they would not all be able to deal with the implementation of RawLam in the same way. The scenarios are designed to consider those differences.

Scenario 0 is the conventional production of glulam. Maximum yield for glulam products in this scenario requires a CT scan and the means to precisely orient a log in front of the saw blades. The log is oriented such that the specified sawing pattern would result in the highest possible yield of boards, informed by detected features and defects in the CT scan. Scenario 1 plans for the extraction of RawLam lamellae from dry boards and shredding the remainders of boards for shavings and sawdust. While it also relies on CT scanning to allocate the RawLam lamellae, it requires less equipment as the remainders are simply shredded. It is important to note that, since the RawLam process extracts lamellae from specific areas of specific boards, it is not limited by through-cuts as is a typical sawmill. In the experiments, this is performed manually however shows potential for automation. Scenario 2 plans the extraction of RawLam lamellae in the wet stage, drying and planing them afterwards and shredding the remainders into wet chips. As for Scenario 1, the whole process involves no complex sawing patterns, and relies on simple plain-sawing before lamella extraction. It is the scenario closest to the current processing in the RawLam experiments. Finally, Scenario 3 relies on the possibility of extracting additional boards in the leftover spaces between the RawLam lamellae. After drying and extraction of the RawLam lamellae, the remainders are processed to extract "push" lumber products. Figure 6 shows the different leftovers configurations after extraction of the RawLam lamellae, which result in varying co-products.

Fig. 5. Evaluated scenarios for glulam and RawLam production

Fig. 6. Typical leftovers from cutting out lamellae in the RawLam method. Since the lamellae are extracted from the log according to the mapping of material properties, they are not necessarily packed tightly to maximize yield, leaving potentially usable areas behind. These can be larger areas well-suited for extracting extra lumber (a), smaller areas that may be used, depending on the minimum size limits (b), or small unusable areas (c).

Co-products cascade assessment

The evaluation of a co-product cascade in the sawmill industry is conventionally done by averaging the production numbers provided by one or more sawmills over minimum five years [14][15][16]. In the present research, an evaluation of average production numbers for the Swedish sawmill industry co-product cascade, which encompass very little glulam, was provided by Norra Timber, as well as numbers for a glulam scenario, based on the numbers of the few specific Swedish sawmills that do produce glulam. The focus is on timber production in Sweden as the RawLam experiments were developed in partnership with Swedish sawmills. Furthermore, sawmills in Sweden are particularly advanced in digitalizing activities, including CT scanning of the log, a step instrumental to RawLam production and therefore highly relevant to consider. However, it is important to note that yields and co-product cascades can vary highly depending on countries and their respective sawmill and forestry industries [17]. The cascade considers glulam / RawLam lamellae, lumber, dry offcuts, chips, shavings and sawdust. Dry offcuts designate larger offcuts generated during the first cutting steps. Chips designate the woods chips generated during cutting operations before the drying step. Shavings designate the wood chips generated during the planing step. Sawdust designates all wood dust generated during various cutting steps. Shavings and sawdust are

considered together in the cascade as both are dry co-products transformed into pellets for energy use. Bark was not considered in the cascade as debarking is done upstream of sawmills in Sweden [18].

The calculation of the cascade was performed based on data obtained during the fabrication of one phase of the RawLam experiments. The allocation of lamellae into the boards obtained from one sawn log out of four in this phase was considered. After allocating the RawLam lamellae based on their performance criteria, push products are allocated in available leftover spaces. Sawdust is accounted for by assuming a 3.2 mm saw kerf both between boards as well as around the perimeter of each lamella, and shavings are accounted for by assuming 2 mm of planing after lamella extraction. As remainders in the RawLam scenarios vary considerably in shape both compared to each other and compared to conventional remainders, it is considered that they are entirely shredded into chips, which results in no dry offcuts present in the cascade. A 4% shrinkage factor was assumed.

Table 1 presents the co-product cascades for each scenario. The modifications in the ratios of lamella/lumber, of chips/shavings, and of (lumber + lamella)/(chips + shavings) are of relevance. The first considers the balance between the two categories of main products, considering that the sawmilling process is being optimized for maximum yield in lamellae. The second considers the balance between the two main categories of co-products, considering that sawmills will favor the chip yield as it can be used for paper pulp, which holds more value than the pellets obtained from shavings and sawdust. The third is key as it compares product and co-products yield, the main variation sought after to understand the impact of the RawLam process and its particularities on lamella production.

Table 1. Co-products cascade for the different scenarios

	Percentage (%)					
	sawn products		co-products			
	lamellae	lumber	wet chips	shavings sawdust	dry offcuts	shrinkage
Sweden - typical cascade	0	50	27	15	4	4
Scenario 0 - Glulam	12	35	27	18	4	4
Scenario 1 - RawLam (dry board extraction)	43	0	0	53	0	4
Scenario 2 - RawLam (wet board extraction)	43	0	32	21	0	4
Scenario 3 - RawLam (push product extraction)	43	25	10	24	0	4

While Scenario 0 features a 47/45 ratio, Scenarios 1 and 2 feature a common 43/53 ratio, and Scenario 3 features a 68/34 ratio. While Scenario 1 and 2 show a decrease in sawn wood product yield, they feature a strong increase in lamella extraction (12 to 43%) and represent the possibility for a sawmill to engage in RawLam production without resorting to more equipment than a CT scan, linear saw, and a circular plunge saw.

They also represent a shift towards a full “pull” approach in sawmilling, where only the desired products are extracted from the log. Scenario 3 introduces a significant improvement of the (lumber + lamella)/(chips + shavings) ratio, and as such is the best possible scenario regarding the cascade amongst those examined, making the most of the resource according to industrial constraints. By reintroducing lumber product extraction in the remainders of the board, this scenario furthermore corresponds to a hybrid push/pull approach. The push product is allocated according to minimal dimensions for lumber products. Such minimal dimensions vary highly across the industry and therefore allow for a flexible allocation and for a significant part of the remaining space to be utilized [13].

Dimensional variations that impact the cascade results also include the thickness of boards. The current planing process assumes the removal of 2 mm from each board to ensure a good enough gluing surface for the lamellae. Since most of the lamellae in this RawLam phase have a thickness of only 10 mm, the amount of planing has a very large impact on the product/co-product ratio. This would be greatly mitigated if thicker 40 mm lamellae were extracted, as is more typical with straight glulam elements. Curved glulam manufacturers require thinner lamellae depending on the resultant curvature of the beams and could provide further points of reference in the comparison performed here. In the same fashion, the kerf width assumption could vary depending on specific equipment and impact the cascade proportions as it modifies the amount of sawdust present in it. Generally, while the increase in lamella production is high across all scenarios, it is to take with precaution as different parameters considered (yields in sawmills, equipment available, dimensions of push products) can vary highly depending on contexts.

Push/pull allocation in the RawLam process

Fig. 7. The updated allocator prototype attempts to fill remaining material on boards with push material (red).

The assessment results not only provide insights into the evolution of the co-product generation when resorting to RawLam, they also provide inputs for an integration of co-products management directly into the allocator, through embedding the three ratios identified into a multi-objective optimization method [19][20][21][22][23]. Thus, the allocation method shifts towards taking environmental stakes into account: finding the ideal lamella, as initially implemented in the RawLam process, becomes balanced with nesting for waste reduction. The current prototypical advancement in the allocator performs the performance-based allocation as before (the “pull” phase) and then subsequently performs another round of allocation to fill in the remaining space on the board with arbitrarily sized boards (the “push” phase). In this instance, there are no limits on the minimum widths or lengths of the extra products, but only a constraint on their aspect ratio: they must be rectangular with their long axes aligned with the main log axis.

Furthermore, as it enables the minimization or maximization of volume for specific co-products according to needs, the integration of ratios into the fitness function also allows for value adjustments. Enabling the adjustment of the (lamella + lumber)/(chips + shavings) ratio depending on the cutting pattern within the allocator therefore allows for a given log to not only be optimized for waste efficiency, but also for maximal value. The integration of co-products management into the allocator also en-

ables an optimization of the carbon sequestration, as it correlates with waste minimization. While the different products in the cascade have graded economic value, they also have different carbon sequestration abilities. The products with the lowest value in the cascade are also the ones with the shortest lifespan and therefore with the lowest carbon sequestration potential. On the other hand, the products with the highest value in the cascade are construction products, which are integrated in buildings with long lifecycles and therefore act as long-term carbon sinks. As the carbon sequestration correlates with value, the cascade can be optimized not only for maximal value, but also for maximal carbon sequestration.

Conclusion

This paper reveals the key differences between the standard sawmilling and glulam production process and the RawLam method in terms of the specific production steps involved and the resultant impacts on co-product ratios. In this way, evaluating the perceived benefits of the RawLam approach to design modelling glulam blanks against broader metrics of economic value and carbon sequestration becomes possible. For prospective new production approaches to gain traction as feasible alternatives to established methods, this alignment is necessary. The expansion of the dimensionality of the allocation process into a multi-objective problem which includes co-products and variations in production steps in addition to matching for mechanical performance poses further challenges on how to evaluate outcomes and determine the best weighting of indicators to target in any given situation: a particular production case might privilege mechanical performance over higher-value co-product generation, whereas another might prioritize the inverse. Exposing this complexity and blurriness in decision-making is therefore also crucial for implementing the method. For a better comparison between methods, the allocator requires both the imposition of dimensional constraints (minimums, maximums, categories of dimensions) as well as estimates of equivalent strength grades from the extracted products.

Further work could focus on the integration of other environmental impacts. As an example, the energy requested for the cuts performed when extracting the lamellae and push products would be a relevant balance to the currently considered indicators, as minimizing it would be necessary, reducing the number of cuts performed on a board. Land use would also be of relevance, as it has been at the core of a long-term debate over the development of forestry, as the use of land for timber resources cultivation can conflict with the preservation of environments, or with other necessary land uses [22]. Beyond specific sustainability indicators, while the variation of major parameters impacts the ability to draw conclusions based on the comparison performed, it allows for particularly efficient sensitivity analysis. Indeed, many of these parameters can be considered to define the dimensions of the push products, to recalibrate a sawing line or to set up a new sawmill. As such, sensitivity studies provide concrete leads into reducing environmental impacts that can be enforced.

As part of a larger effort to integrate a wider segment of the timber value chain into architectural design processes, this work demonstrates how industry-relevant indicators such as the value impacts of the co-product cascade can help steer the design modelling

of engineered timber elements. Leveraging computational modelling methods and connecting information more holistically across the timber value chain has the potential to relate decision-making in architectural design more closely to quantifiable impacts of resource extraction in the forest. As such, design modelling methods that incorporate co-products management, carbon sequestration, product lifespans, but also land use and impact transfer evaluation thus can reveal collateral effects of design decisions and new hidden opportunities.

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